

Stability and strength of cold-formed c-shaped and z-shaped profiles – analytical studies

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Abstract:

This article presents analytical studies of the stability and strength of thin-walled beams with non-standard cross-sectional geometry, manufactured by Zaprom Ltd. The analyses cover four load conditions, for which critical buckling load values were determined. The studies were conducted for three example beams made of innovative profiles designed to improve structural performance. The paper utilizes an approach combining theory based on the principle of conservation of potential energy with numerical analysis using the finite-stripe method (FSM). The results allow for an assessment of the influence of loading conditions and geometric parameters on the forms of instability and critical load values. The analyses provide a basis for further optimization of the thin-walled profile shapes, taking into account both load-bearing efficiency and structural safety.

Keywords: Thin-walled beam; Stability, Analytical studies, Buckling.

1. Introduction

Thin-walled beams are an essential component of many modern engineering structures due to their favorable strength-to-weight ratio. However, their slender geometry makes them particularly susceptible to buckling, which can lead to a sudden loss of structural stability. Accurately predicting the buckling capacity of thin-walled beams requires advanced analytical methods that consider both the geometric nature of the cross-section and the influence of boundary conditions and loads. Analytical studies in this field have explored different aspects of stability, including elastic, dynamic, and thermal buckling, using various theoretical and numerical methods.

HANCOCK [1] reviewed and summarised the major research developments in cold-formed steel structures published during 1999-2001. PAWLAK *et al.* [2] presented current state of knowledge of imperfections in thin-walled steel profiles with modified cross-sectional shapes. MAGNUCKA-BLANDZI [3] described the effective shaping of cold-formed thin-walled channel beams with double-box flanges subjected to pure bending. MAGNUCKA-BLANDZI *et al.* [4] provided the results of numerical and experimental investigations of buckling problems of cold-formed thin-walled channel beams with double-box flanges in pure bending. JASION *et al.* [5] conducted numerical and experimental analysis of buckling and post-buckling behaviour of selected cold-formed C-beams with modified cross-sections and compared them to a classical

one. RHODES AND SEAH [6] investigated the buckling behaviour of cold-formed edge-stiffened thin-walled steel beams subjected to pure moment loading. LAUDIERO AND ZACCARIA [7] presented the numerical calculations of the buckling loads for elastic straight thin-walled beams of open section subjected to any distribution of conservative static loads. ADANY AND SCHAFER [8] presented the derivation for a proposed method which can be used for the decomposition of the stability buckling modes of a single-branched open cross-section thin-walled members into pure bending via finite strip method. PAWLAK *et al.* [9] analysed experimentally and numerically the strength and resistance to loss of stability of thin-walled channel columns. SUDHIRSASTRY *et al.* [10] performed the lateral buckling analysis of cold-formed thin walled channel beams for several combinations of the geometric parameters. GREEDA AND PACZOS [11] investigated the local elastic buckling and limit load of the non-standard thin-walled channel beams subjected to pure bending. BOURIHANE *et al.* [12] presented the examination of the stability of thin-walled beams with open section subjected to arbitrary loads. CHU *et al.* [13] investigated numerically the local and distortional buckling behaviour of cold-formed steel zed-section beams subjected to uniformly distributed transverse loads. KIM *et al.* [14] analyzed coupled stability of thin-walled composite beams with closed cross-section subjected to various forces based on numerical method. HANCOCK AND PHAM [15] developed the Semi-Analytical Finite Strip Method (SAFSM) for thin-walled sections subjected to localised loading to investigate web crippling phenomena. They summarised the SAFSM theory then applied it to the buckling of plates, and channel sections under localised loading. PHAM *et al.* [16] provided a comprehensive analytical and numerical study of elastic buckling of thin-walled channels subjected to different combinations of bending and shear stresses. MAGNUCKI *et al.* [17] studied analytically, numerically and experimentally problems of global and local stability of thin-walled channel beams with drop flanges. PENAVAL *et al.* [18] analyzed the elastic stability of steel thin-walled C- and Z-cross-section beams without lateral restraints. SAMANTA AND KUMAR [19] analysed distortional buckling of simply supported monosymmetric I-beams under three types of load: a central point load, a uniformly distributed load and a uniform sagging moment. SILVESTRE AND CAMOTIM [20] presented the derivation of generalised beam theory (GBT)-based fully analytical formulae to provide distortional critical lengths and bifurcation stress resultant estimates in cold-formed steel C and Z-section members subjected to uniform compression, pure bending and a combination of both. PAVLOVIC *et al.* [21] analysed stochastic vibrations of a viscoelastic nanobeam under axial loadings based on the higher-order nonlocal strain gradient theory and the Liapunov functional method. YU *et al.* [22] presented an analytical study on the distortional buckling of cold-formed steel channel-section beams with circular holes in the web with modified Hancock's solution. MAGNUCKA-BLANDZI [23] described analytically lateral buckling of thin-walled beams under combined load. KOROBEYNIKOV *et al.* [24] studied the buckling of nanostructures using stability criteria of discrete elastic systems. BINH *et al.* [25] presented an improved generalized procedure for dealing with the stability of thin-walled beams under combined symmetric loads based on the energy method.

In this paper analytical studies on the stability of thin-walled beams cover various aspects, including buckling behavior and effects of different loading conditions. The purpose of this article is to present the results of analytical buckling studies of thin-walled beams, with

particular emphasis on various forms of instability and their dependence on structural parameters.

The presented research concerns thin-walled steel beams with nonstandard cross-sectional geometries, introducing innovative profiles designed to improve structural performance. These sections are manufactured by Zaprom Ltd. The tests are aimed at checking the strength of the proposed profiles under specific load conditions. The study integrates theoretical analyses based on the principle of potential energy conservation with numerical simulations performed using the Finite Strip Method (FSM).

2. Analytical studies

The factor influencing the load-bearing capacity of thin-walled bars and beams is the phenomenon of loss of stability. In the case of thin-walled bars/beams, we can distinguish three forms of buckling:

- General or global, which characterizes in the case of a rod its flexural, torsional or flexural-torsional buckling, while in the case of bent beams its lateral-torsional buckling. The shape of the cross-section does not change after buckling,
- Local, which is characterized by the fact that the cross-section of the beam is deformed, while for beams with flat walls the edges of the wall connections do not move,
- Distortional, which, similarly to the local form of buckling, is characterized by cross-section deformation, but the edges connecting two flat walls can move.

The study considers beams of length L , pinned at both ends and loaded with:

- a) two moments of value M applied to both ends of the beam (pure bending) – Load case I (Figure 1)

Figure 1 Loading diagram - pure bending

The values of external forces distributed along the length of the beam are:

$$(2.1) \quad q_x = 0, \quad q_y = 0, \quad q_z = 0.$$

Internal forces are equal to:

$$(2.2) \quad N(x) = 0, \quad M_y(x) = M = M_{max}, \quad M_z(x) = 0, \quad B = 0,$$

- b) uniformly distributed transverse load of intensity q in the plane passing through the shear center - load case II (Figure 2)

Figure 2 Load diagram – load with uniformly distributed force q

The values of external forces distributed along the length of the beam are:

$$(2.3) \quad q_x = 0, \quad q_y = 0, \quad q_z = q,$$

while internal forces:

$$(2.4) \quad N(x) = 0, \quad M_y(x) = 4M_{max} \frac{x}{L} \left(1 - \frac{x}{L}\right), \quad M_z(x) = 0, \quad B = 0,$$

where

$$(2.5) \quad M_{max} = \frac{1}{8} qL^2.$$

- c) concentrated force F applied halfway along the beam at the shear center – load case III (Figure 3)

Figure 3 Load diagram – load with concentrated force F

The values of external forces distributed along the length of the beam are:

$$(2.6) \quad q_x = 0, \quad q_y = 0, \quad q_z = F\delta\left(x - \frac{L}{2}\right),$$

The internal forces are equal to:

$$(2.7) \quad N(x) = 0, \quad M_y(x) = 2M_{max} \times \begin{cases} \frac{x}{L} & \text{for } x \in \langle 0, \frac{L}{2} \rangle \\ 1 - \frac{x}{L} & \text{for } x \in \langle \frac{L}{2}, L \rangle \end{cases}, \quad M_z(x) = 0, \quad B = 0,$$

where

$$(2.8) \quad M_{max} = \frac{1}{4} FL.$$

- d) longitudinal force P applied in the middle of the cross-section – load case IV (Figure 4)

Figure 4 Load diagram - load with longitudinal force P

The values of external forces distributed along the length of the beam are:

$$(2.9) \quad q_x = 0, \quad q_y = 0, \quad q_z = 0.$$

The internal forces are equal to:

$$(2.10) \quad N(x) = -P, \quad M_y(x) = 0, \quad M_z(x) = 0, \quad B = 0.$$

2.1. Second-order equilibrium equations

To describe the displacements of the tested thin-walled beams, a Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) was introduced, where the x -axis is the beam axis, while the y, z axes form the central coordinate system associated with each of the beam cross-sections (Figure 5). The displacements of any point P in the x, y and z axes directions were designated u_P, v_P, w_P . The displacement of the centre of cross-section C in the x -axis direction was designated $u_C = u$, while the displacement of the shear centre S in the y and z axes directions was designated $v_S = v$ and $w_S = w$, respectively. Furthermore, it was assumed that the points lying on the line with coordinates (x, y_R, z_R) are elastically supported and the rotation in the direction parallel to the x -axis is limited.

The following geometric properties of cross-sections are defined:

A – surface area,

J_S – geometric characteristic for free torsion,

J_y, J_z, J_{yz} – axial moments of inertia,

J_ω – segmental moment of inertia,

r_S^2 – polar radius of gyration relative to the shear center,

$\beta_{Sy}, \beta_{Sz}, \beta_\omega$ – cross-section asymmetry arms.

Figure 5 Beam cross-section [26]

The equilibrium equations for a thin-walled beam were determined from the principle of minimum total potential energy

$$(2.11) \quad \delta(U_\varepsilon - W) = 0,$$

where U_ε is the elastic deformation energy, while W is the work of the load.

Potential energy of elastic deformation (MOHRI *et al.* [27], LI [28]) is written in the form:

$$(2.12) \quad U_\varepsilon = U_{el} + U_{en},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.13) \quad U_{el} = & \frac{1}{2} E \int_0^L \left[A \left(\frac{du}{dx} \right)^2 + J_z \left(\frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} \right)^2 + 2J_{yz} \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + J_y \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 \right. \\
& \left. + J_\omega \left(\frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} \right)^2 \right] dx + \frac{1}{2} G \int_0^L J_s \left(\frac{d\psi}{dx} \right)^2 dx \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L [k_y v_R^2 + k_z w_R^2 + k_\psi \psi^2] dx
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.14) \quad U_{en} = & \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L N \left[\left(\frac{dv}{dx} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \right] dx \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L [r_s^2 N + 2\beta_{sz} M_y - 2\beta_{sy} M_z + 2\beta_\omega B] \left(\frac{d\psi}{dx} \right)^2 dx \\
& + \int_0^L \left[M_y \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + M_z \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right] \psi dx + \int_0^L N \left[z_s \frac{dv}{dx} - y_s \frac{dw}{dx} \right] \frac{d\psi}{dx} dx,
\end{aligned}$$

The work of external forces is

$$(2.15) \quad W = \int_0^L (-q_x u + q_y v_Q + q_z v_Q) dx - M_y \frac{dw}{dx} \Big|_0^L + M_z \frac{dv}{dx} \Big|_0^L + Nu \Big|_0^L,$$

where v_Q and w_Q is the displacement of points lying on the axis $Q(x, y_Q, z_Q)$ to which forces of intensity q_y, q_z are applied.

From the principle of minimum total potential energy, a system of second-order differential equations was obtained

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.16) \quad EA \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} &= -q_x, \\
EJ_z \frac{d^4 v}{dx^4} + EJ_{yz} \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} - \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{dv}{dx} \right) + \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (M_y \psi) - z_s \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right) + k_y v_R &= q_y, \\
EJ_y \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} + EJ_{yz} \frac{d^4 v}{dx^4} - \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{dw}{dx} \right) + \frac{d^2}{dx^2} (M_z \psi) + y_s \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right) + k_y v_R &= q_z, \\
EJ_\omega \frac{d^4 \psi}{dx^4} - GJ_s \frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} - \frac{d}{dx} \left[(Nr_s^2 - 2\beta_{sy} M_z + 2\beta_{sz} M_y + 2\beta_\omega B) \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right] + M_y \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} \\
&+ M_z \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} - z_s \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{dv}{dx} \right) + y_s \frac{d}{dx} \left(N \frac{dw}{dx} \right) - (z_R - z_s) k_y v_R \\
&+ (y_R - y_s) k_z w_R + k_\psi \psi = \\
&= (y_R - y_s) (q_z - q_y \psi) - (z_R - z_s) (q_y + q_z \psi),
\end{aligned}$$

In case $q_x = 0$ ($N = \text{const}$), $q_x = 0$ ($N = \text{const}$) and after integrating the first three equations of the above system, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.17) \quad EA \frac{du}{dx} &= N, \\
EJ_z \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + EJ_{yz} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} - Nv + (M_y - z_s N) \psi &= M_z,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
EJ_y \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + EJ_{yz} \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} - Nw + (M_z + y_S N)\psi &= -M_y, \\
EJ_\omega \frac{d^4 \psi}{dx^4} - GJ_s \frac{d^2 \psi}{dx^2} - \frac{d}{dx} \left[(Nr_S^2 - 2\beta_{Sy}M_z + 2\beta_{Sz}M_y + 2\beta_\omega B) \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right] \\
+ (M_y - z_S N) \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + \\
+ (M_z + y_S N) \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} &= (y_Q - y_S)(q_z - q_y \psi) - (z_Q - z_S)(q_y + q_z \psi).
\end{aligned}$$

2.2. Global buckling

The loss of global stability in the first three load cases, the so-called lateral-torsional buckling, is characterized by simultaneous torsion and spatial bending (Fig. 6), while in the fourth load case the buckling form may be flexural, torsional or flexural-torsional.

Figure 6 Torsional buckling of a thin-walled beam [26]

Maximum critical moment $M_{max,kr}$ and critical force P_{kr} calculated by solving the system of equations using the Bubnow-Galerkin method, substituting

$$(2.18) \quad \frac{v}{v_1} = \frac{w}{w_1} = \frac{\psi}{\psi_1} = \sin \frac{\pi x}{L}.$$

In the first three load cases the critical maximum moment $M_{max,kr}$ was

$$\begin{aligned}
(2.19) \quad M_{max,kr} &= C_1 \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 E \frac{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}{J_y} \left\{ C_2 (z_Q - z_S) + C_3 \beta_{Sz} \right. \\
&\quad \left. \pm \sqrt{[C_2 (z_Q - z_S) + C_3 \beta_{Sz}]^2 + \frac{J_y J_\omega}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} \left[1 + \frac{GJ_s}{EJ_\omega} \left(\frac{L}{\pi} \right)^2 \right]} \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

The constants C_i for $i = 1, 2, 3$, depending on the load, took the following values:

- in the load case I

$$(2.20) \quad C_1 = 1, \quad C_2 = 0, \quad C_3 = 1,$$

- in the load case II

$$(2.21) \quad C_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \sqrt{\frac{15}{2(\pi^4 + 45)}} = 1,1325, \quad C_2 = \sqrt{\frac{30}{\pi^4 + 45}} = 0,4590,$$

$$C_3 = (\pi^2 - 3) \sqrt{\frac{5}{6(\pi^4 + 45)}} = 0,5255,$$

- in the load case III

$$(2.22) \quad C_1 = \pi \sqrt{\frac{3}{\pi^2 + 6}} = 1,3659 \quad C_2 = \frac{4}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{3}{\pi^2 + 6}} = 0,5536,$$

$$C_3 = \frac{\pi^2 - 4}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{3}{\pi^2 + 6}} = 0,4062.$$

In the IV load case, the critical force is the smallest eigenvalue of the equation

$$(2.23) \quad A - PB = 0,$$

where

$$(2.24) \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} P_z & P_{yz} & 0 \\ P_{yz} & P_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r_s^2 P_\psi \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & z_s \\ 0 & 1 & -y_s \\ z_s & -y_s & r_s^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$(2.25) \quad P_y = \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_y, \quad P_{yz} = \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_{yz}, \quad P_z = \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_z, \quad P_\psi$$

$$= \frac{1}{r_s^2} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2 EJ_\omega \left[1 + \frac{GJ_s}{EJ_\omega} \left(\frac{L}{\pi}\right)^2 \right]$$

2.3. Distortional buckling

Loss of beam stability can also occur through buckling of the beam flange with simultaneous deformation of the web. This type of buckling is called distortional buckling. In a simplified model of this form of buckling, the beam flange is treated as a beam elastically supported at the edge of its connection to the web (Figure 7). Such a model can be found in HANCOCK [29], SCHAFER AND PERKÖZ [30], TENG *et al.* [31] and PAWLAK *et al.* [26].

Figure 7 Flange buckling [26]

The stresses in the beam can be represented by the formula

$$(2.26) \quad \sigma_x(x, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) = \frac{N}{A} + \frac{(\bar{z} - \bar{z}_C)J_z - (\bar{y} - \bar{y}_C)J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} M_y,$$

where (x, \bar{y}, \bar{z}) is the central coordinate system associated with the beam flange. The geometric properties of the flange cross-section are indicated similarly to those of the entire beam cross-section by adding a single overline.

The internal forces occurring in the flange are

$$(2.27) \quad \bar{N} = \int_{\bar{A}} \sigma_x d\bar{A} = \left(\frac{N}{A} - \frac{\bar{z}_C J_z - \bar{y}_C J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} M_y \right) \bar{A},$$

$$(2.28) \quad \bar{M}_{\bar{y}} = \int_{\bar{A}} \bar{z} \sigma_x d\bar{A} = \frac{\bar{J}_{\bar{y}} J_z - \bar{J}_{\bar{y}z} J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} M_y,$$

$$(2.29) \quad \bar{M}_{\bar{z}} = - \int_{\bar{A}} \bar{y} \sigma_x d\bar{A} = - \frac{\bar{J}_{\bar{y}z} J_z - \bar{J}_{\bar{z}} J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} M_y,$$

$$(2.30) \quad \bar{B} = - \int_{\bar{A}} \bar{\omega} \sigma_x d\bar{A} = 0.$$

After simplification $\bar{v}_P = 0, \bar{w}_P = 0$ i $k_\psi = 0$ the displacements of the beam flange are

$$(2.31) \quad \bar{v} = (\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S) \bar{\psi},$$

$$(2.32) \quad \bar{w} = -(\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S) \bar{\psi}.$$

The elastic deformation energy of the beam flange after introducing the internal forces into equation (12) is equal to

$$(2.33) \quad U_{el} = \frac{1}{2} E \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} \int_0^L \left(\frac{d^2 \bar{\psi}}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} G \bar{J}_S \int_0^L \left(\frac{d\bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx,$$

$$(2.34) \quad U_{en} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L [\bar{r}_P^2 \bar{N} + 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} \bar{M}_{\bar{y}} - 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} \bar{M}_{\bar{z}}] \left(\frac{d\bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx + \\ + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \left[(\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S) \frac{d^2 \bar{M}_{\bar{y}}}{dx^2} - (\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S) \frac{d^2 \bar{M}_{\bar{z}}}{dx^2} \right] \bar{\psi}^2 dx$$

where

$$(2.35) \quad \bar{r}_P^2 = \frac{\bar{J}_{\bar{y}} + \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}}{\bar{A}} + \bar{y}_P^2 + \bar{z}_P^2, \\ \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} = \bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}} + (\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S)^2 \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} - 2(\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S)(\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S) \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}} + (\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S)^2 \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}, \\ \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} = \bar{\beta}_{S\bar{y}} + \bar{y}_S - \bar{y}_P, \quad \bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} = \bar{\beta}_{S\bar{z}} + \bar{z}_S - \bar{z}_P,$$

The nonlinear part of the elastic deformation energy can be written as

$$(2.36) \quad U_{en} = \frac{1}{2} J_N \int_0^L N \left(\frac{d\bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} J_{M1} \int_0^L M_y \left(\frac{d\bar{\psi}}{dx} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} J_{M2} \int_0^L \frac{d^2 M_y}{dx^2} \bar{\psi}^2 dx,$$

where

$$(2.37) \quad J_N = \bar{r}_P^2 \frac{\bar{A}}{\bar{A}}, \\ J_{M1} = \frac{(\bar{z}_C \bar{r}_P^2 \bar{A} - 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} - 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}}) J_z - (\bar{y}_C \bar{r}_P^2 \bar{A} - 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{z}} \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}} - 2\bar{\beta}_{P\bar{y}} \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}) J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}, \\ J_{M2} = \frac{[(\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S) \bar{J}_{\bar{y}} + (\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S) \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}}] J_z - [(\bar{z}_P - \bar{z}_S) \bar{J}_{\bar{y}\bar{z}} + (\bar{y}_P - \bar{y}_S) \bar{J}_{\bar{z}}] J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}.$$

The critical loads were calculated using the Ritz method from the equation

$$(2.38) \quad \delta(U_\varepsilon) = 0.$$

Assuming the shelf rotation angle in the form

$$(2.39) \quad \bar{\psi}(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \psi_m \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L}$$

The equation is obtained in the form

$$(2.40) \quad \det(K_L - M_{max}K_G) = 0 \quad \text{lub} \quad \det(K_L - PK_G) = 0.$$

Matrice K_L for all load cases is:

$$(2.41) \quad [K_L]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} m^2 \left[G\bar{J}_s + m^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 E\bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} \right] & \text{for } m = k, \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases}$$

Matrices K_G are respectively equal:

- in the load case I

$$(2.42) \quad [K_G]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} m^2 J_{M1} & \text{for } m = k \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k' \end{cases}$$

- in the load case II

$$(2.43) \quad [K_G]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} \frac{2}{3} m^2 J_{M1} - \frac{2}{\pi^2} (J_{M1} - 4J_{M2}) & \text{for } m = k \\ -\frac{8}{\pi^2} mk \frac{m^2 + k^2}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} [1 + (-1)^{m+k}] J_{M1} & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases},$$

- in the load case III

$$(2.44) \quad [K_G]_{mm} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \left[\frac{1}{2} m^2 J_{M1} - \frac{1 - (-1)^m}{\pi^2} (J_{M1} - 4J_{M2}) \right],$$

$$(2.45) \quad [K_G]_{mk} = -\frac{\pi^2}{2L} \frac{4}{\pi^2} \left\{ \frac{mk}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} \left[(m^2 + k^2)(1 + (-1)^{m+k}) - (m+k)^2 \cos \frac{(m-k)\pi}{2} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - (m-k)^2 \cos \frac{(m+k)\pi}{2} \right] J_{M1} - \left[\cos \frac{(m-k)\pi}{2} - \cos \frac{(m+k)\pi}{2} \right] J_{M2} \right\},$$

If a diaphragm occurs in the middle of the beam length, the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length can only be an even number. Therefore, the flange rotation angle is approximated by

$$(2.46) \quad \bar{\psi}(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \psi_m \sin \frac{2m\pi x}{L}$$

then

$$(2.47) \quad [K_L]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} 4m^2 \left[G\bar{J}_s + 4m^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{L} \right)^2 E\bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_P} \right] & \text{for } m = k, \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases}$$

$$(2.48) \quad [K_G]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} 2m^2 J_{M1} & \text{for } m = k \\ -\frac{8}{\pi^2} mk \frac{m^2 + k^2}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} [1 - (-1)^{m+k}] J_{M1} & \text{for } m \neq k' \end{cases}$$

- in the load case III

$$(2.49) \quad [K_G]_{mk} = \frac{\pi^2}{2L} \times \begin{cases} m^2 J_N & \text{for } m = k \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k' \end{cases}$$

In load cases I and IV, the formulas for the critical load can be presented explicitly

$$(2.50) \quad M_{max,kr} = \frac{G\bar{J}_s + E\bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_p} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2}{J_{M1}},$$

$$(2.51) \quad P_{kr} = \frac{G\bar{J}_s + E\bar{J}_{\bar{\omega}_p} \left(\frac{\pi}{L}\right)^2}{J_N}.$$

2.4. Local buckling

Loss of local stability manifests itself as buckling of individual beam walls.

In this study, a simplified buckling model was adopted, treating the individual beam walls as plates with length L , width h and thickness t , which are

- supported on four edges - span walls (Figure 8),

Figure 8 Span wall model [26]

- supported on three edges and with one free edge - cantilever walls (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Cantilever wall models [26]

A local coordinate system associated with the beam wall under consideration was introduced, as shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The elastic strain potential energy for the plate can be represented as

$$(2.52) \quad U_{\varepsilon} = U_{el} + U_{en},$$

where

$$(2.53) \quad U_{el} = \frac{1}{2} D \int_0^L \int_0^h \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial \eta^2} \right)^2 - 2(1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial \eta^2} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial x \partial \eta} \right)^2 \right] \right\} d\eta dx$$

$$(2.54) \quad U_{en} = \frac{1}{2} t \int_0^L \int_0^h \sigma_x \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{w}}{\partial x} \right)^2 d\eta dx$$

The stresses are equal to

$$(2.55) \quad \sigma_x(x, \eta) = -\frac{P}{A} + \frac{z(\eta)J_z - y(\eta)J_{yz}}{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2} M_y(x),$$

Let σ_1 denote the greatest compressive stress, and σ_2 the stress occurring in the middle of the length of the opposite edge and let $\psi = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1}$, then in the case of span and cantilever walls, in which the maximum compressive stresses occur on the pin-supported edge, the following relations apply (Figure 8, Figure 9b):

$$(2.56) \quad \sigma_1 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, 0 \right), \quad \sigma_2 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, h \right).$$

In the case of cantilever walls, where the maximum compressive stresses occur at the free edge (Figure 9a):

$$(2.57) \quad \sigma_1 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, h \right), \quad \sigma_2 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, 0 \right).$$

To summarize the stresses

$$(2.58) \quad \sigma_x(x, \eta) = -f_M(x) g_M(\eta) \sigma_1 = -\kappa \frac{\pi^2 D}{th} f_M(x) g_M(\eta),$$

where κ is the local instability parameter.

Function $f(x)$ depends on the load case and is equal to:

- in the load case I and IV

$$(2.59) \quad f_M(x) = 1,$$

- in the load case II

$$(2.60) \quad f_M(x) = 4 \frac{x}{L} \left(1 - \frac{x}{L}\right)$$

- in the load case III

$$(2.61) \quad f_M(x) = \begin{cases} 2 \frac{x}{L} & \text{dla } 0 \leq x \leq \frac{L}{2}, \\ 2 \left(1 - \frac{x}{L}\right) & \text{dla } \frac{L}{2} < x \leq L \end{cases},$$

However, the function $g_M(\eta)$ equals

$$(2.62) \quad g_M(\eta) = (1 - \psi) \frac{\eta}{h} + \psi, \quad \text{when } \sigma_1 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, h\right), \quad \text{then } \eta_1 = h$$

or

$$(2.63) \quad g_M(\eta) = (\psi - 1) \frac{\eta}{h} + 1, \quad \text{when } \sigma_1 = -\sigma_x \left(\frac{L}{2}, 0\right), \quad \text{then } \eta_1 = 0.$$

The maximum critical moment can be calculated from the formula

$$(2.64) \quad M_{max,cr} = \sigma_{1,cr} \frac{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}{z_1 J_z - y_1 J_{yz}} = \kappa_{cr} \frac{\pi^2 D}{th} \frac{J_y J_z - J_{yz}^2}{z_1 J_z - y_1 J_{yz}},$$

where $y_1 = y(\eta_1)$ i $z_1 = z(\eta_1)$.

However, the critical force is equal to

$$(2.65) \quad P_{max,cr} = \sigma_{1,cr} A = \kappa_{cr} \frac{\pi^2 D}{th} A,$$

The critical stresses were calculated using the Ritz method based on the principle of minimum total potential energy.

$$(2.66) \quad \delta(U_\varepsilon) = 0.$$

For span walls, the deflection was approximated by the series

$$(2.67) \quad \tilde{w} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L} \cos \frac{n\pi \eta}{h}$$

Limiting to a few dozen ingredients, i.e. $m = 1, \dots, M, n = 1, \dots, N$.

Potential energy can be represented in matrix form

$$(2.68) \quad U_{\varepsilon l} = \frac{1}{2} \tilde{w}^T K_L \tilde{w}, \quad U_{\varepsilon n} = -\frac{1}{2} \kappa \tilde{w}^T K_G \tilde{w},$$

where

$$(2.69) \quad \tilde{w}^T = [w_{11}, w_{21}, \dots, w_{M1}, w_{12}, \dots, w_{MN}]$$

and

$$(2.70) \quad [K_L]_{ij} = D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda^2} U_{mk}^{22} V_{nl}^{00} + 2U_{mk}^{20} V_{nl}^{02} + \lambda^2 U_{mk}^{00} V_{nl}^{22} - 2(1 - \nu)[U_{mk}^{20} V_{nl}^{02} - U_{mk}^{11} V_{nl}^{11}] \right\}$$

$$[K_G]_{ij} = D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \hat{U}_{mk}^{11} \hat{V}_{nl}^{00}$$

for $i = (n - 1)M + m, j = (k - 1)M + l$

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{mk}^{rs} &= \frac{2}{L} \left(\frac{L}{\pi}\right)^{r+s} \int_0^L \frac{d^r}{dx^r} \left(\sin \frac{m\pi x}{L}\right) \frac{d^s}{dx^s} \left(\sin \frac{k\pi x}{L}\right) dx \\
V_{nl}^{rs} &= \frac{2}{h} \left(\frac{h}{\pi}\right)^{r+s} \int_0^h \frac{d^r}{dy^r} \left(\sin \frac{n\pi y}{h}\right) \frac{d^s}{dy^s} \left(\sin \frac{l\pi y}{h}\right) dy \\
\widehat{U}_{mk}^{rs} &= \frac{2}{L} \left(\frac{L}{\pi}\right)^{r+s} \int_0^L f_M(x) \frac{d^r}{dx^r} \left(\sin \frac{m\pi x}{L}\right) \frac{d^s}{dx^s} \left(\sin \frac{k\pi x}{L}\right) dx \\
\widehat{V}_{nl}^{rs} &= \frac{2}{h} \left(\frac{h}{\pi}\right)^{r+s} \int_0^h g_M(y) \frac{d^r}{dy^r} \left(\sin \frac{n\pi y}{h}\right) \frac{d^s}{dy^s} \left(\sin \frac{l\pi y}{h}\right) dy
\end{aligned}$$

Matrice K_L can be written in the form

$$(2.71) \quad [K_L]_{ij} = D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{m^2}{\lambda} + n^2\lambda\right)^2 & \text{dla } m = k \wedge n = l \\ 0 & \text{dla } m \neq k \vee n \neq l \end{cases}$$

However, the integrals \widehat{U}_{mk}^{11} are equal:

- in the load case I and IV

$$(2.72) \quad \widehat{U}_{mk}^{11} = \begin{cases} m^2 & \text{for } m = k \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k' \end{cases}$$

- in the load case II

$$(2.73) \quad \widehat{U}_{mk}^{11} = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{3\pi^2} (m^2\pi^2 - 3) & \text{for } m = k \\ -\frac{8}{\pi^2} mk \frac{m^2 + k^2}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} [1 + (-1)^{m+k}] & \text{for } m \neq k' \end{cases},$$

- in the load case III

$$(2.74) \quad \widehat{U}_{mk}^{11} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2\pi^2} (m^2\pi^2 - 1 + (-1)^m) & \text{for } m = k \\ -\frac{4}{\pi^2} mk \frac{(m^2 + k^2)(1 + (-1)^{m+k}) - (m+k)^2 \cos \frac{(m-k)\pi}{2} - (m-k)^2 \cos \frac{(m+k)\pi}{2}}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases}.$$

If we consider the diaphragm at the middle of the beam length

$$(2.75) \quad \widehat{U}_{mk}^{11} = \begin{cases} \frac{m^2}{2} & \text{for } m = k \wedge m, k - \text{even} \\ -\frac{8}{\pi^2} mk \frac{(m^2 + k^2)}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} \left(1 - (-1)^{\frac{m+k}{2}}\right) & \text{for } m \neq k \wedge m, k - \text{even} \\ 0 & m, k - \text{odd} \end{cases}$$

or when we substitute

$$(2.76) \quad \tilde{w} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_{mn} \sin \frac{2m\pi x}{L} \cos \frac{n\pi y}{h}$$

then

$$(2.77) \quad [K_L]_{ij} = D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \begin{cases} \left(4 \frac{m^2}{\lambda} + n^2\lambda\right)^2 & \text{for } m = k \wedge n = l \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k \vee n \neq l \end{cases}$$

$$(2.78) \quad \hat{U}_{mk}^{11} = \begin{cases} 2m^2 & \text{for } m = k \\ -\frac{8}{\pi^2} mk \frac{(m^2 + k^2)}{(m^2 - k^2)^2} (1 - (-1)^{m+k}) & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases}$$

The integral \hat{V}_{nl}^{00} is

$$(2.79) \quad \hat{V}_{nl}^{00} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(1 + \psi) & \text{for } n = l \\ \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{nl}{(n^2 - l^2)^2} [1 - (-1)^{n+l}] (1 - \psi) & \text{for } n \neq l \end{cases}$$

The critical values of the local instability parameter κ for the span walls and for selected values of the boundary stress ratio ψ are presented in the graphs (Figure 10 - Figure 12).

Figure 10 Graph of κ_{kr} depending on the ratio of the plate length to its width $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ for the parameter $\psi = 1$ (span walls)

Figure 11 Graph of κ_{kr} depending on the ratio of the plate length to its width $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ for the parameter $\psi = 0$ (span walls)

Figure 12 Graph of κ_{kr} depending on the ratio of the plate length to its width $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ for the parameter $\psi = -1$ (span walls)

For cantilever walls, the deflection was approximated by the series

$$(2.80) \quad \tilde{w} = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} w_m \frac{\eta}{h} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{L}$$

By limiting to a finite number of ingredients, i.e. $m = 1, \dots, M$.

Similarly to the case of span walls, the potential energy can be presented in the matrix form, where

$$(2.81) \quad \tilde{w}^T = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_M]$$

and

$$(2.82) \quad \begin{aligned} [K_L]_{mk} &= D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \begin{cases} \frac{2}{3} m^2 \left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} (1-\nu) + \frac{m^2}{\lambda^2} \right) & \text{for } m = k, \\ 0 & \text{for } m \neq k \end{cases} \\ [K_G]_{mk} &= D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} \psi \right) \hat{U}_{mk}^{11} & \text{for } \eta_1 = h, \\ [K_G]_{mk} &= D \frac{\pi^4}{4Lh} \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{2} \psi \right) \hat{U}_{mk}^{11} & \text{for } \eta_1 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The critical values of the local instability parameter κ for cantilever walls and for a boundary stress ratio of $\psi = 1$ are shown in the graph (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Graph of κ_{kr} depending on the ratio of the plate length to its width $\lambda = \frac{L}{h}$ for the parameter $\psi = 1$ (cantilever walls)

The critical values of the parameter κ for other values of the boundary stress ratio ψ can be calculated as follows:

$$(2.83) \quad \kappa_{kr} = \frac{4}{3+\psi} \kappa_{kr, \psi=1} \quad \text{for } \eta_1 = h$$

or

$$(2.84) \quad \kappa_{kr} = \frac{4}{1+3\psi} \kappa_{kr,\psi=1} \quad \text{for} \quad \eta_1 = 0.$$

2.5. Analytical solutions results

The results of the analytical calculations presented in this chapter were obtained using a specialized program that uses the analytical formulas described here. This program, named GUI, was developed in MATLAB and authored by MARCIN RODAK [32]. This section presents the results obtained for double-bend C-sections and Z-sections. The C-sections were bent in two planes as shown in Figure 14 and named C1 and C2, respectively. The Z-sections were bent in the planes shown in Figure 14. The critical loads in bending were obtained for beams with a length of $L = 420$ mm, and in compression, $L = 800$ mm.

Figure 14 Tested cross-sections and load plane

Results were obtained for the following material constants:

- Young's modulus - $E = 2,0 \cdot 10^5$ MPa,
- Kirchhoff's modulus - $G = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} = 7,6923 \cdot 10^4$ MPa,
- Poisson's ratio - $\nu = 0,3$.

Table 1 presents the results obtained for channel C1. The lowest critical load values for bending were obtained for the local mode of stability loss (web buckling). Using the finite strip method (FSM), the critical moment value for pure bending was $M_{max,kr} = 0,6298$ kNm, and the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length was 9 (buckling half-wave length 46.67 mm). Buckling occurred through local stability loss (Figure 16). The nearly 30% lower critical load values presented in Table 1 result from a simplified model of local stability loss, where the flange walls were treated as non-cooperating plates.

In the compression case, the lowest critical load was obtained for distortional buckling of the flange. This result is significantly lower than the FSM result. This is a consequence of the simplified distortional buckling model, which does not take into account the effect of the stiffness of the web and the rest of the profile on the critical load required for flange buckling.

In the finite strip method, the lowest critical force was obtained for local buckling (Figure 18) with a value of $P_{kr} = 50,73$ kN (the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length was 17, and the buckling half-wave length was 47.06 mm). The error between the critical forces obtained by the two methods was also approximately 30%.

Table 1 Critical loads for profile C1. In load cases I, II, III the beam length was $L=420$ mm, in case IV $L=800$ mm

Buckling form	Load case					
	I	II		III		IV
	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	q_{kr} [kN/m]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	F_{kr} [kN]	P_{kr} [kN]
Global	99,52	67,22	3049	68,44	65,19	59,611
Distortional	-	-	-	-	-	7,4599
Local	0,4509 (web)	0,4940 (web)	22,40 (web)	0,5538 (web)	5,274 (web)	37,219 (web)

Figure 15 The critical moment diagram obtained using the finite strip method for profile C1 in load case I

Figure 16 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile C1, load case I)

Figure 15 and Figure 17 presents the graphs of the critical moment $M_{max,kr}$ in the load case I and the critical force P_{kr} in the load case IV, depending on the length of the buckling half-wave for the C1 profile, respectively.

Figure 17 The critical force diagram obtained by the finite strip method for the C1 profile in the IV load case

Figure 18 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile C1, load case IV)

Table 2 presents the results obtained for channel C2. Similarly to the bent channel C1, the lowest critical load value was obtained for the local mode of stability loss, but through buckling of the flange. In the finite strip method, the critical moment value $M_{max,kr} = 2,817$ kNm was obtained (Figure 19) (the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length was 15, and the buckling half-wave length was 28 mm), and buckling also occurred through local stability loss of the flange (Figure 20).

Table 2 Critical loads for profile C2. In load cases I, II, III the beam length was $L=420$ mm, in case IV $L=800$ mm

Buckling form	Load case						
	I		II		III		IV
	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	q_{kr} [kN/m]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	F_{kr} [kN]	P_{kr} [kN]	
Global	16,05	17,18	779,0	20,43	194,6	59,61	
Distortional	5,288	12,80	580,6	38,84	369,9	7,460	
Local	2,108 (flange)	2,219 (flange)	100,6 (flange)	2,428 (flange)	23,12 (flange)	37,22 (web)	

Figure 19 The critical moment diagram obtained by the finite strip method for the C2 profile in load case I

Figure 20 Buckling form obtained by the finite strip method (profile C2, load case I)

Table 3 presents the results obtained for the Z1-section. In bending, the lowest critical load value was obtained for the local mode of stability loss (web buckling). Using the finite strip method, the critical moment value for pure bending was $M_{max,kr} = 0,3161$ kNm (Figure 21)(the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length was 10, and the buckling half-

wave length was 42.0 mm). This means that the critical load values presented in Table 3 were approximately 30% lower than those obtained using the FSM method. In compression, the lowest critical load value was obtained for the overall beam buckling. This result is comparable to the finite strip method (Figure 22), which was $P_{kr} = 5,474$ kN.

Table 3 Critical loads for profile Z1. In load cases I, II, III the beam length was $L=420$ mm, in case IV $L=800$ mm

Buckling form	Load case					
	I	II		III		IV
	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	q_{kr} [kN/m]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	F_{kr} [kN]	P_{kr} [kN]
Global	16,44	10,70	485,3	10,67	101,6	5,444
Distortional	0,2438	0,2166	9,823	1,075	10,24	8,719
Local	0,2502 (web)	0,2678 (web)	12,15 (web)	0,2957 (web)	2,816 (web)	20,93 (web)

Figure 21 The critical moment diagram obtained by the finite strip method for profile Z1 in load case I

Figure 22 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile Z1, load case I)

Figure 23 The critical force diagram obtained by the finite strip method for profile Z1 in the load case IV

Figure 24 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile Z1, load case IV)

Table 4 presents the results obtained for the Z2-section. In bending, the lowest critical load value was obtained for the local stability mode (web buckling). Using the finite strip method, the critical moment value for pure bending was $M_{max,kr} = 0,9583$ kNm (the number of buckling half-waves along the beam length was 8, and the buckling half-wave length was 52.5 mm). Therefore, the critical load values presented in Table 4 were approximately 23% lower than those obtained using the FSM method. In compression, the lowest critical load value was obtained for distortional buckling of the beam. This result is significantly lower than that obtained using the finite strip method, where the lowest critical force value was obtained for the global buckling mode of $P_{kr} = 12,036$ kN, which is practically the same as that obtained using the analytical method.

Table 4 Critical loads for profile Z2. In load cases I, II, III the beam length was $L=420$ mm, in case IV $L=800$ mm

Buckling form	Load case						
	I		II		III		IV
	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	q_{kr} [kN/m]	$M_{max,kr}$ [kNm]	F_{kr} [kN]	P_{kr} [kN]	
Global	220,5	134,8	6113	128,6	1225	12,41	
Distortional	-	-	-	-	-	1,708	
Local	0,7354 (web)	0,8029 (web)	36,41 (web)	0,8979 (web)	8,551 (web)	29,340 (web)	

Figure 25 The critical moment diagram obtained by the finite strip method for the Z2 profile in load case I

Figure 26 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile Z2, load case I)

Figure 27 The critical force diagram obtained by the finite strip method for the Z2 profile in the IV load case

Figure 28 Buckling shape obtained using the finite strip method (profile Z2, load case IV)

A comparison of critical moments for different bending loads is shown in Figure 29. The analysis of these results shows clear differences in the resistance of the investigated cross-sections to local buckling under bending conditions. Among the examined variants, the highest values of the critical moment were obtained for cross-section C2. In all loading schemes considered, the values exceeded 2.0 kNm, reaching approximately 2.43 kNm in the case of a concentrated load applied at mid-span. This indicates that cross-section C2 exhibits the greatest resistance to local buckling and can be regarded as the most advantageous in terms of load-bearing capacity among the analyzed profiles.

The second highest performance was observed for cross-section Z2, for which M_{CR} ranged between approximately 0.7 and 0.9 kNm depending on the type of loading. Although these values are significantly lower than those obtained for C2, cross-section Z2 demonstrates much better performance compared to cross-sections C1 and Z1. The latter are characterized by the lowest resistance to local buckling, with critical bending moment values not exceeding 0.55 kNm and with only minor differences between them.

The influence of the loading scheme on M_{CR} is noticeable, particularly for cross-section C2, where the transition from moment loading to concentrated load results in an increase of approximately 0.3 kNm in the critical value. In the case of cross-sections with lower resistance (C1 and Z1), this effect is minimal.

Figure 29 Comparison of critical moments for different loads

Figure 30 presents a comparison of critical forces for compression load. The highest values of the critical compressive force (F_{CR}) were obtained for cross-sections C1 and C2, both reaching 37 kN. The second highest performance was observed for cross-section Z2, which demonstrates a noticeably lower resistance to local buckling compared to C1 and C2, yet still relatively high. The critical compressive force reached approximately 29 kN, which is about 20% lower than that of the best-performing profiles. The lowest resistance was recorded for cross-section Z1, with F_{CR} of only about 21 kN. This value is nearly half of that obtained for C1 and C2, clearly limiting its suitability for applications involving significant compressive forces.

Figure 30 Comparison of critical forces for compression

The analyses have shown that the resistance of the cross-sections to local buckling depends on the type of loading. Under bending, the best performance is demonstrated by cross-section C2, which achieves more than four times higher capacity compared to the weakest profiles (C1 and Z1). Under axial compression, the highest resistance to local buckling was obtained for cross-sections C1 and C2. Cross-section Z2 represents an intermediate solution in both cases, while Z1 proves to be the least favorable profile under both bending and compression.

3. Conclusions

The article focuses on the analysis of stability and load-bearing capacity of thin-walled beams with non-standard cross-sectional geometries, manufactured by Zaprom Sp. z o.o. The aim of the study was to determine the critical buckling loads under different loading conditions and to identify the dominant forms of instability. Analyses were carried out for three innovative profiles (channel and Z-sections), designed to enhance load-bearing efficiency and structural safety.

The research methodology combined a theoretical approach, based on the principle of potential energy conservation, with numerical calculations using the Finite Strip Method (FSM). Four loading scenarios were considered: pure bending, uniformly distributed transverse load, concentrated force at mid-span, and axial compression. For each case, equilibrium equations were formulated, and critical buckling moments and forces were determined using the Bubnov-Galerkin method.

Three main forms of instability were distinguished: global (flexural–torsional), local (wall buckling), and distortional (cross-sectional deformation with flange displacement). The results

showed that, for the analyzed profiles, the lowest critical loads were most often associated with local buckling of the walls, confirmed by both theoretical models and FSM calculations. In the case of axial compression, distortional or global buckling frequently governed the structural response.

The comparative analysis of profiles C1, C2, Z1, and Z2 highlighted significant differences between simplified analytical models and FSM results, with discrepancies reaching 20–30%. This was mainly due to the inability of analytical models to fully capture the interaction of cross-sectional components. The most favorable buckling resistance was observed in profile C2, which demonstrated improved stability of the flanges.

The obtained results provide a basis for further optimization of thin-walled cross-sectional shapes, taking into account both load-bearing efficiency and structural safety. The combination of analytical methods with FSM enables a more precise assessment of beam behavior and facilitates the design of more efficient engineering solutions.

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